

Aerial Transportation, Deployment and Retrieval of Dexterous Dual Arm Rolling Robot for Power Line Maintenance: Field Validation

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Abstract—This paper presents the application of an aerial-deployable dual arm rolling robot developed for the realization of maintenance operations on power lines, validated through field tests in a real power line. The system consists of a quadrotor used as carrier platform for the transportation, deployment and retrieval of a lightweight and compliant anthropomorphic dual arm system (LiCAS). The arms are equipped with a drive wheel that allows them to move along the cable to conduct the installation of devices while the aerial platform stays at the landing area. The proposed approach avoids the problems of operating while flying in terms of positioning accuracy and energy efficiency, reducing also significantly the load on the power line compared to the case in which the multi-rotor has to perch. The paper describes the mechanisms implemented for the deployment and retrieval of the arms on the power line and for the installation of a customized model of bird flight diverter on the power line, as well as the system architecture, reporting results and practical aspects derived from the experimental validation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of aerial robots for the realization of inspection and maintenance (I&M) operations on power lines, one of the most extensive and critical infrastructures in any country, has demonstrated its potential for enhancing current procedures carried out by human operators in highly risky conditions, involving climbing the pylons or using elevated working platforms and manned helicopters to reach the transmission lines [1]. In order to avoid the inconveniences of conventional approaches, several robotic solutions have been proposed in last decades for the realization of these operations on power transmission lines [2], [3], distinguishing typically between climbing robots, aerial robots [4], [5], [6], and platforms implementing hybrid operation modes [7], [8], [9].

The interest in the development and application of aerial robots for power line I&M is due to the ease and speed of reaching and moving along this kind of infrastructure, overcoming obstacles like the pylons or the devices installed on the cables. Unlike vision-based inspection operations [10], [5], the realization of maintenance tasks involves physical and electrical interactions with high voltage power lines [11], [12]. Some works exploit the electromagnetic features of the power lines, proposing methods for recharging the batteries of the drone [4], [13]. Different research concepts have been proposed for increasing safety in the realization of manipulation operations on power lines, for example for the installation of bird flight diverters and other devices [14]. Other references consider the use of aerial robots to assist human workers deployed on the power lines [15], [16], [17].

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Fig. 1. Aerial transportation, deployment, and retrieval of dual arm rolling robot for the installation of a customized model of bird flight diverters. Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I8Ou9y5vrc0>

The realization of maintenance tasks involving the installation of devices on the transmission lines, such as bird flight diverters [18], electrical spacers, or vibration dampers, requires the development of aerial platforms providing manipulation capabilities [19] with a certain degree of dexterity, accuracy, and payload capacity. A general purpose aerial robot capable of perching and installing different types of devices with a single arm is presented in [9]. An automated mechanism is developed in [20] to perform the installation of electrical spacers. A dual arm teleoperation system is proposed in [21] for installing complex helical devices typically used in the Spanish power grid. A control framework intended to automate the installation of bird diverters, tested in simulation, is described in [22].

This paper relies on our previous works on aerial robotics for power line inspection and maintenance developed as part of the AERIAL-CORE project [1]. In [11] we reported the first experiments of an aerial manipulator interacting with a high voltage (15 kV) power line, comparing the effectiveness of electrical shielding and insulation for protecting the aerial robot from the electrostatic discharge. The concept of a deployable dual arm for power line maintenance and the design of a self-stabilizing system is described in [23], presenting preliminary validation tests in a testbench. A comparative study of three manipulation modes (while flying, holding, and perching) for the aerial robot is presented in [24]. The leader-follower kinesthetic teleoperation system developed in [21] facilitates the intervention of the human operator in unexpected situations by providing a natural and

intuitive interface for controlling the arms, being also easily deployable on site thanks to its very low weight.

Based on this, the main contribution of this paper is the validation in a real power line of the aerial transportation, deployment and retrieval of a lightweight and compliant anthropomorphic dual arm equipped with a rolling base intended to conduct maintenance operations. This concept is illustrated in Figure 1. Two mechanisms are incorporated on the multi-rotor platform for this purpose: a preloaded spring-hook mechanism for holding and deploying the dual arm on the power line [23], and a cable suspended hook for retrieving the arms [25].

The main novelties with respect to our previous works are the following:

- Development of full system capable of conducting the complete operation: aerial deployment, installation of devices, and retrieval.
- Development and testing of a cable-suspended hook-handle mechanism for retrieving the dual arm, identifying those factors affecting the required accuracy.
- Experimental validation of the system in a real power-line scenario, reporting several practical aspects derived from the conducted tests.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the developed system. Section III provides an overview of the modeling, whereas Section IV covers the validation methodology. Field tests are reported in Section V, presenting some conclusions on Section VI.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

A. Platform Description

The aerial-deployable dual arm rolling robot developed for this work is shown in Figure 2. It consists of two systems. On the one hand, the manipulator developed for conducting the maintenance operation is based on the Lightweight and Compliant Anthropomorphic Dual Arm System Model 1 (LiCAS A1)¹, modified to incorporate the rolling base driven by a servo actuator, which is placed in such a way that the center of mass of the robot is under the power line [23], achieving passive stable perching in this way. The robot integrates a Raspberry Pi 3B computer board that executes the control program of the LiCAS, including the automated installation of bird diverters, which is launched from the Ground Control Station (GCS) through a SSH session over a WiFi link. A lightweight kinesthetic teleoperation interface [21] is also installed along with the GCS so the operator of the LiCAS can take control of the arms in case of need.

On the other hand, the aerial platform that serves as carrier is the X4 quadrotor employed in our previous works [23], [25], providing 4.5 kg payload, with a maximum take-off weight (MTOW) of 9.5 kg. It employs 21×7 inches propellers with DJI E2000 motors, 12S 4500 mAh LiPo batteries, and the CUAUV5 flight controller running Ardupilot. Accurate position control outdoors is achieved with RTK-GPS (Real-Time Kinematics, Global Positioning System).

Fig. 2. Two views of the dexterous dual arm rolling robot and the multi-rotor equipped with the pre-loaded hook and the double cable suspended hook for the deployment and retrieval operations.

Two mechanisms are incorporated to the aerial robot for implementing the deployment and retrieval maneuvers. The preloaded hook-handle mechanism described in [23] is used to detach the LiCAS from the multi-rotor when it is supported by the power line. The geometry of the hook is such that the arms are held due to the action of their own weight, but it is retracted by a preloaded spring when this force is released as the rolling base lays over the cable. A novel double-cable suspended hook implements the complementary operation for grasping the deployed robot from the handle. The length, mass, stiffness, and damping of the cables, along with the shape and mass of the hook, are design parameters determined empirically based on the identification of oscillations on the suspended mechanism, which are caused mainly by three factors: the accelerations induced by the motion of the aerial platform, the aerodynamic drag, and the aerodynamic downwash [15].

B. Installation of Devices

The operation to be conducted by the robot is the installation of a customized model of bird flight diverter, shown in Figure 1, on a power line section. The procedure is illustrated in Figure 3. The device, weighting 30 grams, consists of a 3D printed body frame with an orange rubber strip used as visual marker, a 20 mm section washer used for the magnetic grasping with the arms, and a hook-like aluminum rod (4 mm section) for perching the device on the cable. The devices are loaded by a human operator in the two arrays at both sides of the arms. Each array can carry up to four devices. The installation operation is implemented as a sequence of Cartesian way-points for the arms [23], repeated for each device, changing only the position of the corresponding device in the array for its grasping. In order to avoid the complexity and additional weight of actuated grippers, the end effector of the arms is equipped with a neodymium permanent magnet that allows to grasp firmly and retrieve from the array the bird diverter by the washer attached to the body frame. Once the aluminum hook is introduced around the cable, the device is detached from the magnetic gripper by applying an impulsive motion downwards with the end effector to exert a tangential force that overcomes the friction and magnetic force between the washer and the magnet.

¹<https://licas-robotic-arms.com/>

Fig. 3. Sequence of images describing the installation of bird flight diverters on a power line testbed using the dual arm rolling robot.

III. SYSTEM MODELING

The kinematic model of the deployable dual arm aerial manipulation robot is represented in Figure 4. As usual, three reference frames are defined in the first place: the inertial Earth fixed frame $\{\mathbf{E}\}$, the multi-rotor body frame $\{\mathbf{B}\}$, and the dual arm base frame $\{\mathbf{0}\}$ attached at the midpoint of the shoulder structure, with the X-axis pointing forwards and the Z-axis pointing upwards. The anthropomorphic kinematics of the arms includes four positioning joints, three at the shoulder and one at the elbow. Denoting by q_j^i the rotation angle of the j -th joint of the i -th arm, the joints are: shoulder flexion/extension (q_1^i), shoulder adduction/abduction (q_2^i), lateral/medial rotation (q_3^i), and elbow flexion/extension (q_4^i). The upper arm and forearm link lengths are denoted by L_1 and L_2 , respectively, whereas D is the separation between both arms. The analytical resolution of the forward/inverse kinematics of this configuration can be found in [23], [21].

Three additional links are introduced in this configuration: the U-shaped handle attached at the shoulder structure, with length L_0 , the hook mechanism at the base of the multi-rotor used in the deployment operation, L_h , and the cable suspended hook used in the retrieval, with length L_c . As indicated in Figure 4, q_h represents the rotation angle of the hook mechanism at the base of the aerial platform, which is actuated by the preloaded spring and by the weight of the dual arm manipulator until this is deployed on the line, whereas q_0 is the rotation angle of the handle that holds the arms, similarly to a double pendulum. On the other hand, the two-cable configuration, derived from our previous works [15], [25], adds three additional degrees of freedom: a Δx - Δy displacement of the handle with respect to the multi-rotor base, and a torsion angle $\Delta\psi$ in yaw angle due to the double cable configuration. System dynamics can be derived following the usual Euler-Lagrange formulation [25].

Once the dual arm robot is deployed on the line, it behaves as a stable pendulum since its center of mass (taking the contact point of the wheel with the power line as pivot point) is around 4 cm under the cable. The self-stabilizing control of this platform was already addressed in our previous work [23]. Denoting by r the radius of the rolling wheel actuated by the servo, the linear speed of the platform is $v = r\omega$, where ω is the angular speed of the wheel.

IV. VALIDATION METHODOLOGY

A. Validation Scenario

Field tests were conducted in a section of transmission line at the following coordinates: $38^\circ 08' 33.6''\text{N}$ $3^\circ 09' 28.9''\text{W}$. This area is a crop field close to the ATLAS Flight Center in Villacarrillo (Jaen, Spain). The cables were supported by two 12 m height pylons, deploying the dual arm at the midpoint of the line where the altitude is 9 m due to the sag. This section of transmission line was disconnected from the power grid before the realization of the validation tests for safety reasons, although the experimental results presented in [11] evidenced that the components employed in the dual arm rolling platform are not affected by the electrostatic discharge when interacting with a 15 kV power line.

B. Experimental Setup

The components and equipment involved in the realization of the experiments are listed below:

- Multi-rotor aerial platform with two 4.500 mAh LiPo batteries and LiPo battery testers with acoustic alarm for low voltage detection.
- LiCAS A1 dual arm rolling robot for installing four customized clip type diverters carried in two linear arrays, integrating the Raspberry Pi 3 on-board computer, the 3S 2.500 mAh LiPo battery, and the 5V 10.000 mAh power bank for the Raspberry Pi.
- Ground Control Station (GCS) laptop for executing the Mission Planner² software, for integrating the measurements of the GPS RTK, and for launching the dual arm control program executed on the Raspberry Pi board.
- WiFi router for communicating the GCS laptop with the onboard computer of the dual arm.
- GPS RTK antenna with tripod and receiver connected to the GCS laptop.
- Walki-Talkies with headsets for communication between the multi-rotor pilot and the operator of the robotic arms.
- Van for the transportation of the equipment.

The experiments presented in this paper involved the participation of at least two people: the pilot of the aerial platform, and the dual arm aerial robot operator at the GCS.

C. Validation Procedure

The execution of the operation with the aerial deployable dual arm manipulator is as follows:

- 1) The vehicle driven by the aerial robot operators is parked in a convenient area close to the installation

²<https://ardupilot.org/planner/>

Fig. 4. Kinematic model of the dual arm aerial manipulation robot in deployment (left and middle) and retrieval (right) configurations, including the reference frames, joint angles, and link lengths.

points, such that it can be easily accessed without disturbing the road traffic.

- 2) The GCS is setup on a table or in the vehicle. The GPS RTK antenna is connected to the Mission Planner to start the survey process required to achieve a desired positioning accuracy (taking around 20 minutes for 0.5 m accuracy in open sky conditions).
- 3) The aerial platform is placed in the field, in a take-off position as close as possible to the installation point where the surrounding vegetation does not interfere. Batteries are connected, battery voltage is checked, and connection between the autopilot and the Mission Planner is established.
- 4) The dual arm manipulator is installed in the multi-rotor, supported by the preloaded hook mechanism used in the deployment. The devices to be installed on the power line are loaded in the linear arrays.
- 5) The WiFi network for communicating the onboard computer of the arms and the GCS laptop is activated. The computer board is powered then to allow the connection to the network, previously configured to be connected automatically when detected.
- 6) The control program of the arms is launched through SSH (secure shell) session from the GCS laptop.
- 7) The aerial deployment operation is conducted in the first place. The dual arm will start the installation operation once deployed on the line by the aerial platform, while this is going back to the landing zone.
- 8) The aerial retrieval operation is carried out once the devices are installed on the power line.

The last two phases will be described in more detail in the experimental validation section.

V. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION: FIELD TESTS

A. Aerial Transportation and Deployment

The first phase of the operation is represented in the image sequence depicted in Figure 5. The dual arm rolling robot is

held by the preloaded hook-handle mechanism attached to the multi-rotor base. The devices to be installed on the line are loaded on the two arrays (left and right) of the arms. The robot is initially located at the take-off and landing area close to the desired deployment point. The human operators involved in the validation test are the pilot and the operator of the dual arm at the ground control station (GCS).

Fig. 5. Aerial transportation and deployment on the power line of the dual arm rolling robot, showing on-board camera field of view (FoV).

The time evolution of the multi-rotor platform during the aerial transportation and deployment is represented in Figure 6, whereas Figure 7 shows the 3D trajectory. The platform approaches from above to the deployment point until the rolling base lays on the cable and the preloaded hook-handle mechanism is released. This event can be easily identified at $t = 70$ s by the sudden drop in the electric power consumption (from 1000 W to 500 W) as well as by the increase in the multi-rotor altitude (up to 10 m) once the mass is released. This first phase takes two minutes from take-off to landing.

Fig. 6. Evolution of multi-rotor position, velocity, attitude and electric power during the aerial transportation, deployment (left) and retrieval (right).

Fig. 7. 3D trajectory representing the aerial transportation, deployment, and retrieval phases of the dual arm rolling robot on the power line.

B. Dual Arm Operation

Once the arms are deployed on the line, they start executing the installation of the bird flight diverters carried in the two arrays, following the procedure illustrated in Figure 3. The arms perform the installation of four devices in 60 seconds, rolling along the power line at 14 cm/s to maintain a separation distance between devices of 1 m. A picture of the devices installed on the power line is shown in Figure 8. A key aspect here is the reliability when grasping the devices with the magnetic gripper and detaching them by exerting an impulsive tangential force. This factor is determined by the width of the opening through which the device is introduced, and by the dimension of the magnetic washer attached to the plastic body used by the magnetic gripper (see Figure 1).

Thanks to the very low weight of the robot (3 kg total), the increase in the line sag is negligible and thus the rolling base can easily move along it with much lower energy consumption compared to the case in which the entire aerial platform has to perch [9] or operate while flying. A single 3S LiPo battery (12-14 V) with 2500 mAh capacity provides an operation time between 20 and 30 minutes.

Fig. 8. Four customized bird flight diverters installed by the dual arm rolling robot on the power line.

C. Aerial Retrieval

The sequence of images from the retrieval phase is shown in Figure 9, presenting the graphical results in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The multi-rotor is now equipped with a double-cable suspended hook used to retrieve the dual arm by the handle, incorporating a couple of neodymium magnets to facilitate the alignment and grasping. Previous experiments evidenced the difficulty for guiding the hook towards the handle when the mass and damping of the suspended cables are relatively low (see the orange strings in Figure 1), since the aerodynamic downwash introduced by the propellers and the oscillation of the hook due to the pendulum effect had a significant negative impact on the positioning accuracy [25]. For the validation tests described here, a pair of elastic polypropylene tying bands for transport were used, presenting two benefits with respect to the ones from Figure 1: 1) the string elasticity results in smoother transitions from load-free to load-retrieved states, a kind of passive compliance for the altitude controller, and 2) the increased mass and damping of these strings reduced significantly the oscillations of the suspended hook. The total retrieval time from take-off to landing is 160 seconds.

Fig. 9. Aerial retrieval of the dexterous dual arm rolling robot.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper reported the field validation on a real transmission line of the aerial transportation, deployment and retrieval of a very low weight (3 kg) dexterous dual arm rolling robot developed for the installation of bird flight diverters. The robot demonstrated its practical application and the benefits of the proposed solution in terms of ease of transportation, fast deployment, and low impact on the power line in terms of sag increase. The paper described the mechanisms, system architecture and the experimental setup. Field tests also demonstrated the tolerance of the developed robot to adverse outdoor conditions, including dust, mug, wind, and slight rain in some of the tests campaigns.

As future work, it is necessary to increase the capacity for carrying devices, and reduce the retrieval time, redesigning the cable-hook-handle mechanism in a more convenient way to reduce oscillations raised during this maneuver, taking into account wind and the aerodynamic downwash effect.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Ollero, A. Suarez, J. M. Marredo, G. Cioffi, R. Penicka, G. Vasiljevic, and A. Viguria, "Application of intelligent aerial robots to the inspection and maintenance of electrical power lines," *Robotics and Automation Solutions for Inspection and Maintenance in Critical Infrastructures; Now Publishers: Delft, The Netherlands*, 2024.
- [2] J. Katrasnik, F. Pernus, and B. Likar, "A survey of mobile robots for distribution power line inspection," *IEEE Transactions on power delivery*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 485–493, 2009.
- [3] A. B. Alhassan, X. Zhang, H. Shen, and H. Xu, "Power transmission line inspection robots: A review, trends and challenges for future research," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 118, p. 105862, 2020.
- [4] N. Iversen, O. B. Schofield, L. Cousin, N. Ayoub, G. Vom Bögel, and E. Ebeid, "Design, integration and implementation of an intelligent and self-recharging drone system for autonomous power line inspection," in *2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 4168–4175.
- [5] Z. Wang, Q. Gao, J. Xu, and D. Li, "A review of uav power line inspection," in *Advances in Guidance, Navigation and Control: Proceedings of 2020 International Conference on Guidance, Navigation and Control, ICGNC 2020, Tianjin, China, October 23–25, 2020*. Springer, 2022, pp. 3147–3159.
- [6] J. Xing, G. Cioffi, J. Hidalgo-Carrió, and D. Scaramuzza, "Autonomous power line inspection with drones via perception-aware mpc," in *2023 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1086–1093.
- [7] N. Pouliot, P.-L. Richard, and S. Montambault, "Linescout technology opens the way to robotic inspection and maintenance of high-voltage power lines," *IEEE Power and Energy Technology Systems Journal*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–11, 2015.
- [8] W. Chang, G. Yang, J. Yu, Z. Liang, L. Cheng, and C. Zhou, "Development of a power line inspection robot with hybrid operation modes," in *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 973–978.
- [9] J. Marredo, A. Petrus, M. Trujillo, A. Viguria, and A. Ollero, "A novel unmanned aerial system for power line inspection and maintenance operations," in *2024 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 602–609.
- [10] R. Janssen, D. Roverso *et al.*, "Automatic autonomous vision-based power line inspection: A review of current status and the potential role of deep learning," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 99, pp. 107–120, 2018.
- [11] A. Suarez, R. Salmoral, P. J. Zarco-Periñan, and A. Ollero, "Experimental evaluation of aerial manipulation robot in contact with 15 kv power line: Shielded and long reach configurations," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 94 573–94 585, 2021.
- [12] V. D. Hoang, T. McRae, E. Ebeid, C. L. Bak, and H. Zhang, "Modeling electric spark discharges on drones in contact with high-voltage power lines and lab equivalent tests," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 2025.
- [13] D. Stuhne, V. D. Hoang, G. Vasiljevic, S. Bogdan, Z. Kovacic, A. Ollero, and E. S. M. Ebeid, "Design of a wireless drone recharging station and a special robot end effector for installation on a power line," *IEEE access*, vol. 10, pp. 88 719–88 737, 2022.
- [14] J. Cacace, S. M. Orozco-Soto, A. Suarez, A. Caballero, M. Orsag, S. Bogdan, G. Vasiljevic, E. Ebeid, J. A. A. Rodriguez, and A. Ollero, "Safe local aerial manipulation for the installation of devices on power lines: Aerial-core first year results and designs," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 13, p. 6220, 2021.
- [15] A. Suarez, R. Salmoral, A. Garofano-Soldado, G. Heredia, and A. Ollero, "Aerial device delivery for power line inspection and maintenance," in *2022 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 30–38.
- [16] Y. Wang, H. Paul, R. Miyazaki, R. R. Martinez, T. Kominami, R. Ladig, and K. Shimonomura, "Active translatory drive system with docking capability for uav power line inspection," in *2022 IEEE/ASME International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Mechatronics (AIM)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 689–694.
- [17] A. Afifi, M. van Holland, and A. Franchi, "Toward physical human-robot interaction control with aerial manipulators: Compliance, redundancy resolution, and input limits," in *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 4855–4861.
- [18] M. Ferrer, V. Morandini, R. Baumbusch, R. Muriel, M. De Lucas, and C. Calabuig, "Efficacy of different types of "bird flight diverter" in reducing bird mortality due to collision with transmission power lines," *Global Ecology and Conservation*, vol. 23, p. e01130, 2020.
- [19] A. Ollero, M. Tognon, A. Suarez, D. Lee, and A. Franchi, "Past, present, and future of aerial robotic manipulators," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 626–645, 2022.
- [20] F. Zorić, S. Flegarić, G. Vasiljević, S. Bogdan, and Z. Kovačić, "Autonomous installation of electrical spacers on power lines using magnetic localization and special end effector," *Machines*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 510, 2023.
- [21] A. Suarez, A. Gonzalez-Morgado, and A. Ollero, "Lightweight and compliant bilateral teleoperation system with anthropomorphic arms for aerial and ground service operations," in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 15 685–15 691.
- [22] S. D'Angelo, F. Pagano, F. Ruggiero, and V. Lippiello, "Development of a control framework to autonomously install clip bird diverters on high-voltage lines," in *2023 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 377–382.
- [23] A. Suarez, S. R. Nekoo, and A. Ollero, "Ultra-lightweight anthropomorphic dual-arm rolling robot for dexterous manipulation tasks on linear infrastructures: A self-stabilizing system," *Mechatronics*, vol. 94, p. 103021, 2023.
- [24] A. Suarez and A. Ollero, "Dual arm aerial manipulation while flying, holding and perching: Comparative case study," in *Iberian Robotics conference*. Springer, 2022, pp. 259–270.
- [25] G. D'Ago, M. Selvaggio, A. Suarez, F. J. Gañán, L. R. Buonocore, M. Di Castro, V. Lippiello, A. Ollero, and F. Ruggiero, "Modelling and identification methods for simulation of cable-suspended dual-arm robotic systems," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 175, p. 104643, 2024.